

Solubilities of some Tetraalkylammonium Bromides in a Few Solvents of High Dielectric Constant¹.

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Solubilities of some tetraalkylammonium bromide have been determined in water, N-methylformamide, N,N'-dimethylformamide and in formamide, at different temperatures. It is found that the solubility in water decreases with the length of the alkyl chain (R-) of the R_4N^+ ions while it increases directly with the length in the other solvents mentioned above; also the solubility increases with the rise in temperature in all the solvents within the temperature range studied here. The results appear to support the views that while in aqueous solutions, R_4N^+ ions are hydrophobic in nature, they feel at home (i.e., lyophilic) in other solvents, probably on account of the similarity of their structure and their common organic origin.

In view of the current interest in the study of the properties of salts containing the tetraalkylammonium ions (R_4N^+), it appears desirable to determine the solubilities of some of these salts in aqueous and non-aqueous solvents in the hope of throwing some light on the nature of their interaction with the solvents of different natures as well as to provide the useful solubility data to workers in this field. In spite of a large number of studies on the solutions of salts containing these ions during recent years, very little attention seems to have been paid to determine their solubilities, either in water or in other solvents, at different temperatures. Only the solubilities of Bu_4NI and Pen_4NI , in aqueous solution, have been reported in the literature². In view of our current programme on the study of the properties of the tetraalkylammonium ions, it was considered worthwhile to determine the solubilities of some available salts containing R_4N^+ ions in water and in some other solvents which have been engaging our attention for the last few years. The present communication, reports the solubilities of some R_4NBr salts in water, formamide, N-methylformamide (NMF) and in N,N'-dimethylformamide (DMF) at different temperatures.

EXPERIMENTAL

The solvents, formamide, NMF and DMF, were suitably purified as given in the literature^{3,4}. The conductance of the solvents used was less than 10^{-5} mho and the purity of this order was considered quite sufficient for the solubility measurements. Conductivity water was used for experiments in aqueous solutions. The R_4NBr salts were purified by fractional crystallisation from suitable solvents or their mixtures⁵. Analysis of some purified samples showed that the purity was better than 99.5%. The crystallised samples were dried and kept in a vacuum desiccator.

1. Work in parts, supported from the financial assistance of the CSIR, India, and the Society of the Sigma XI and RESA of USA.
2. F. Franks and D. L. Clarkes, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1967, **71**, 1155.
3. R. Gopal and R. K. Srivastava, *Ibid.*, 1962, **66**, 3704.
4. G. R. Leader and J. F. Gormley, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 5731.
5. B. E. Conway, R. E. Verrall and J. E. Desnoyers, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1966, **62**, 2738.

In view of the short supply of the R_4NBr salts and of some of the solvents studied here, it was decided to employ the synthetic method for the determination of solubilities. Although the method may not be very accurate, it is convenient and economical since the solvent and the solute can be recovered after the experiment. Known amounts of the solvent and the solute were sealed in a pyrex glass ampule. Three samples of identical composition were prepared for each experiment. These ampules were kept inside a thermostat whose temperature could be raised slowly, in 0.1° intervals, when desired. The temperature of the bath was held constant ($\pm 0.03^\circ$) for sufficient time to ensure saturation. The ampules were shaken regularly and the temperature at which the last crystal, in an ampule, disappeared was taken as the saturation temperature of the sample. Usually, this temperature was found to be the same for all the three samples of the same composition. Generally, the mean of the three temperatures was taken. Ampules for other compositions were prepared and their saturation temperatures determined. As these salts were found to have a great tendency for supersaturation, they did not show any sign of crystallisation, once dissolved completely, even after two days when shaken. So the observations could only be made for the rising temperatures. From the plot of the solubility against temperature, solubilities at 25° , 30° and 35° , were read off from the solubility curve and are given in Table I.

TABLE I

Solubilities of some tetraalkylammonium bromides at different temperatures

Solvent	Temp.	Solubility of (in gms/100 gms. solvent)				
		Me_4NBr	Et_4NBr	Pr_4NBr	Bu_4NBr	Hep_4NBr
Water	25°	94.50	48.35	22.75	12.35	Insoluble
	30°	99.90	52.93	25.57	14.30	
	35°	105.30	56.16	28.40	16.30	
Formamide	25°	11.51	62.92	147.5	191.3	216.5
	30°	12.73	64.91	149.5	195.1	223.6
	35°	14.17	66.87	151.6	199.4	231.7
N-methylformamide (NMF)	25°	3.19	24.10	66.25	85.30	121.9
	30°	3.63	27.80	70.65	90.25	126.8
	35°	4.17	31.50	75.05	95.25	131.7
N,N'-dimethylformamide (DMF)	25°	0.38	31.45	44.80	62.32	91.90
	30°	0.41	34.90	48.55	66.15	98.40
	35°	0.44	38.35	52.24	69.93	104.9

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It may be observed from Table I that the solubilities of R_4NBr salts, in water, decrease with the increase in the length of the alkyl chain of the R_4N^+ ions; in other solvents studied here, solubility increases with the length of the alkyl group and appears to level off for the larger R_4N^+ ions. The temperature coefficient of solubility, in every case, is positive and solubility in different solvents is in the order :

From the solubility curves, the heats of solution for the different R_4NBr salts, in different solvents, have been estimated and are given in Table II.

TABLE II

Heats of solution, $\Delta H_{solution}$, of tetraalkylammonium bromides at different solvents.

Solvent	$\Delta H_{solution}$ in Kcals./mole of				
	Me_4NBr	Et_4NBr	Pr_4NBr	Bu_4NBr	Hep_4NBr
Water	1.87	2.72	4.02	4.62	—
Formamide	3.66	0.98	0.69	0.57	0.48
N-methylformamide	4.86	4.78	1.81	1.74	1.38
N,N'-dimethylformamide	3.44	3.32	2.49	1.63	1.21

As may be noticed from Table II, $\Delta H_{solution}$, in water, increases with the length of the alkyl chain; this implies that the heat of solvation, $\Delta H_{solvation}$, would be smaller for the larger ions. This is, perhaps, expected since the electrostatic ion-solvent interaction would be smaller, the larger the ion although the hydrogen-bonded structure promotion in water would be favoured by the larger ions; the latter process, perhaps, involves negligible heat. So the larger $\Delta H_{solution}$ of the larger R_4N^+ ions are, perhaps, reasonable. The heats of solution in other solvents (i.e., formamide, NMF and DMF), given in Table II, are in the reverse order, i.e., the larger the R_4N^+ ion the smaller the $\Delta H_{solution}$. This would imply a larger heat of solvation $\Delta H_{solvation}$ and a stronger R_4N^+ -solvent interaction. This deduction is quite at variance with the usual experience and difficult to interpret since the larger the radius of the ion, the smaller the electrostatic-ion-solvent interaction. It could be that since the R_4N^+ ions and the solvents are similar in structure and origin, there may be strong dispersion interaction between the alkyl chains of the R_4N^+ ions and the solvent molecules like, say, in the larger organic molecules; this interaction would lead to a smaller positive heat of solution and a larger heat of solvation. This suggestion is, rather, a tentative one since the $\Delta H_{solution}$ data, obtained here, corresponds to the saturated state which are fairly concentrated. For more reliable conclusions, heats of solution at infinite dilution should be obtained⁶. Even in aqueous solutions, the heat of solutions data, reported here, should be treated with reserve as these are based on very scanty solubility data.

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6. $\Delta H_{solution}$, obtained by Bhatnagar and Criss for Me_4NI , Et_4NI and Pr_4NI in DMF, are 4.01, 3.42 and 1.996 kcals. per mole. which are in the order as given in Table II of this paper. We are obliged to these workers for making the data available to us. In aqueous solutions, the data obtained by them are in the reverse order of that obtained here.